

LEADERSHIP STYLES AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE IN THE ADVERTISING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Organizational cultures are often created by organizational leaders and then sustained through the telling of organizational stories and celebration of organizational heroes. Leaders in organizations are responsible for creating and managing organizational culture that is geared towards enhanced organizational performance. Organizational leaders are believed to have the unique talent and ability to understand and work with culture in place in any organization and ultimately expected to destroy the culture when it is seen as not achieving the desired objectives. The aim of this study is to find out how organizational leadership and organizational culture impact on organizational performance in the advertising industry. This study adopts a single case research approach and uses the purposive sampling method to select the participants. About 40 staffs of a particular advertising company in Lagos was sampled. The respondents which include staffs and the directors were administered with questionnaires. The results of the collected questionnaires were analyzed with the use of simple statistics. The study finds that integrity, security, high ethical standard, routine process and continuous learning were considered by leadership as organizational culture. In addition, organizational leadership and organizational culture were reported to have a huge impact on the organization through rewards and promotions, culture that is receptive to change, good working relations among the staff. Finally, transformational leadership style was found to be the most preferred approach to leadership in the case study company. The result also shows that behavior pattern, symbols and symbolic actions, believe, attitudes and values were ways of accessing organizational culture. The study concludes that organizational leadership and organizational culture are intertwined and interwoven and that both organizational leadership and organizational culture are important in the overall performance of an organization.

Keyword: Advertising, Organizational Culture, Organizational Leadership, Organizational Performance, Nigeria.

1.0 Introduction

There is a need for every leader to grasp and understand the nature and impact of organizational culture on an organization, so as to communicate new vision and also ensure that subordinates are committed

to visions of the organization. Chandler and Black (2007) stresses that organizational cultures are often created by company founders and then sustained through the telling of organizational stories and celebration of organizational heroes. The author adds that organizational leaders are responsible for creating and managing organizational culture. Hence, they are believed to have the unique talent and ability to understand and work with culture in place in any organization and ultimately expected to destroy the culture when it is seen as not achieving the desired goals of the organization. Schein (2004) opines that leaders create and manage culture, meaning that the unique talent of organizational leaders is their ability to understand and work with culture and it is an ultimate act of leadership to destroy culture when it is viewed as dysfunctional. Leadership plays an important role in shaping and maintaining organizational culture. Deal and Kennedy (2000) argues that organizational culture is beliefs and values that are shared by members of an organization which in turn originates from the founder of the organization and sustained by telling the stories of the organization and celebrating their past heroes. Williams (2007) reports that leadership and organizational culture are intertwined and interwoven and this in turn affect the performance of an organization. He further describes organizational culture as set of key values, beliefs, and attitudes shared by organizational members. The researcher adds that the shared values and beliefs have strong influence on the people in the organization and ultimately on the organizational performance. These organizational cultures will dictate how employees act, dress and perform on their work (Cole, 2002; Dalton, 2005; Buchanan et al., 2005). The contemporary definition of organizational culture includes what is valued; the leadership style, the language and symbols, the procedures and routines, and the definitions of success that characterizes an organization (Deal and Kennedy, 2000; Chandler and Black, 2007). It is a specific collection of values and norms that are shared by people and groups in an organization and these control the way they interact with each other and with stakeholders outside the organization.

Ahmadi et al. (2012) posits that organizational values are beliefs and ideas, about, what kinds of goals members of an organization should pursue and the appropriate kinds or standards of behaviour organizational members should use to achieve these goals. From organizational values develops organizational norms, guidelines or expectations that prescribe appropriate kinds of behaviour by employees in any particular situations and control the behaviour of organizational members towards one another. Desson and Clouthier (2010) mentions that organizational culture can change with time depending on such factors as the environment in which the organization operates and economic climate prevailing at the period. Ajagbe and Ismail (2015) argues that the introduction of technology by the organization into its operations can also alter the culture of the organization. They further add that this is likely to bring about efficient use of resources that will lead to the attainment of the organizational goals. Starling (2008) finds that organizational culture will also be influenced by such factors as nature of the business in which the organization is engaged in and the type of industry. Hofstede (2001) opines that the nation in which the organizations exist is also influenced by the culture of the nation. Hence, he mentions that there are national and regional cultural groupings that affect the behaviour of an organization and he identified five dimensions of culture as power distance, uncertainty avoidance, individualism vs. collectivism, masculinity vs. femininity and long versus short term orientation. Obasan (2012) concludes that the culture in banking industry is different from that of advertising

industry where creativity is the central focus. Deal and Kennedy (2000) finds that organizations have very differing cultures as well as subcultures. Corporate culture can be said to be part of organizational culture. As all of the definitions of corporate culture identify the critical element of sharing within a group, it is important to consider how an individual behaves within the group context. From group dynamic theory, the individual in a group setting has basically three primary needs (Madu, 2010; Manbula, 2009; Moi et al., 2001). The first of these is to feel that he is part of the group by developing a viable role and being recognized by other members of the group. This involves a compromise of maintaining a distinct and separate identity at the same time as being seen as a group member. Second, there is a need for him to feel powerful, able to influence and control whilst accepting the needs of others to do the same. This can lead to conflict but can also help to formulate the roles of individuals within the group. Third, there is a need to feel accepted by the group and to achieve the basic security and intimacy that comes with that feeling of acceptance (Fay and Denison, 2009; Harari, 2002; Jin, 2010; Mullin, 2005). These factors are important whether it is a totally new group that is being formed or where a new member is entering an existing group. Schein (2004) saw these needs as reflecting the basic human needs for security, mastery of the environment (influence and control) and love (acceptance and intimacy). Business organization just as in advertising firms or agencies sees corporate culture as part of the organizational culture. The leadership and the organizational culture adopted by the organization affects its performance. It is on the basis of this that, the study intends to investigate how organizational leadership and organizational culture interact to influence organizational performance in the advertising industry. Figure 1 indicates the conceptual framework of the study revealing the relationship among the variables under investigation such as organizational leadership, organizational culture and organizational performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Research Framework

2.0 Review of Related Studies

2.1 Organizational Leadership

Organizational leadership was viewed by Cohen and Elmgick (2002) as the ability of superiors to direct, guide and motivate people towards the attainment of given set of goals in an organization. The source of influence may be formal such as that provided by the possession of managing rank in an organization

or informally outside the organization structure. Most organizational theorists agree that effective leadership is one of the most important contributors to overall organizational success. Bello-Imam and Ojeifo (2007) concludes that the quality of an organization's leadership determines the quality of the organization itself. Chandler and Black (2007) said in leadership, we communicate clearly, show the team the vision, and show the individual the vision. Then we manage the agreement that comes out of that. They authors concludes that leadership is clear in its communication. It also welcomes feedback to make sure that the vision is communicated and relationship between the leader and the group, organizational norms, structure and technology of the organization, the variety of tasks are maintained by variety of subordinate (Belias and Koustelios, 2014; Chathoth and Olen, 2002; Cohen and Elmick, 2002). However, most organizational leader's effort are geared towards thinking rather than doing. Nonetheless, leaders can only get results by working hard. The tasks of leaders are complex and difficult, and selfdiscipline is necessary in order to master and practice the skills of leadership. Dalton (2005) considers organizational leadership as an essential part of business and society. The author adds that sport coaching is a role that necessitates leadership. He said research studies have proved otherwise, as results have been conflicting to findings generally in leadership studies. The result of their study showed that coaches were reticent to describe their activities as leadership or themselves as leaders. However, coaches were articulate when describing their role in developing the players under them as leaders. Agbonifoh et al. (2005) were of the view that the successful organization has one major attribute that sets it apart from the unsuccessful organization; dynamic and effective leadership. Obiwuru et al. (2012) posits that there are two types of leadership and they are different from one another. Sharma and Sharma (2010) opines that transactional leaders display both constructive and corrective behaviours. Constructive behaviour entails contingent reward, and corrective dimension imbibes management by exception. Contingent reward involves the clarification of the work required to obtain rewards and the use of incentives and contingent reward to exert influence. It considers follower expectations and offers recognition when goals are achieved. The clarification of goals and objectives and the provision of recognition once goals are achieved result in individuals and groups achieving expected levels of performance. Rabbani et al. (2014) stresses that transformational leader's behaviour originates in the personal values and beliefs of the leader and motivates subordinates to do more than expected. Buchanan et al. (2005) said the vision of the leadership must be clear, goals must be clear, consistent, stable and challenging.

2.2 Organizational Culture

Rabbani et al. (2014) observes that cultures are formed by leaders and therefore culture do not exist on their own. Cultures in organizations begin when leaders formulate group like an organization and the founder influence the way of doing things in shared assumptions to perform the task and behave in a definite way. Yukl (2013) mentions that culture is socially learned and transmitted by members, it provides the values for behaviour within an organizations. The core values of an organization begin with its leadership, which will then evolve to a leadership style. Schein (2004) argues that subordinates will be led by these values and the behaviour of both parties should become enhanced in line when strong unified behaviour, values and beliefs have been developed, a strong organizational culture emerges. Ogbonna and Harris (2000) notes that the founder creates and shapes the cultural traits of

the organization during the process of forming the organization. As the organization grows and develop over the years the created culture of the organization exerts an influence on the leaders and shape the actions and style of the leader. Larsson (2007) opines that the advertising industry is seen as very individual-focused and it was stated that individual's talent and hard work play a very big role. However, individual's skill and creativity can only come out in the right culture. Starling (2008) stresses that corporate culture is not just a set of beliefs; it is comprised of a set of values, patterns of behaviour, and artifacts like the physical layout of an organization, and accounts and narratives that reinforce those values. As companies have expanded across the globe, the idea of culture has become more complex as diverse ethnic backgrounds, languages, and geographies have become part of the culture. Duncan (2002) writes that a corporate culture reflects the personality of an organization; it is sometimes described as the way we do things, it is the pattern of shared values that structure the way an organization's employees work and interact with each other and with stakeholders.

2.3 Organizational Performance

Ajagbe (2007) argues that organizational performance comprises of the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs or goals and objectives. Recent research carried out by scholars have attempted to demonstrate the impact of human resources management on firm performance (Ogbari et al., 2016; Okibo and Shikanda, 2016). However, earlier research in this field linked individual human resources management practices such as training, selection appraisals and compensation to firm financial performance (Obiwuru et al. 2011; Ogbonna and Harris, 2000). Hence, performance can be referred to as doing the work, as well as achieving laid down objectives. Yukl (2008) views organizational performance as the outcomes of work because they provide the strongest linkage to the strategic goals of an organization, customer satisfaction and economic contributions. The researcher go further to say, the term "performance management and measurement" refers to any integrated, systematic approach to improving organizational performance to achieve strategic aims and promote an organization's mission and values (Borman, 1991; Ajagbe et al., 2015). In that sense organizational performance management is quite different than individual performance management which specifically targets the personal performance of an employee although the latter comprises an essential part of the overall organizational performance framework. Williams (2007) stresses that a performance management system aims at improving the results of people's effort by linking these to the organization's goals and objectives. Yukl (2013) concludes that performance management is an avenue through which employees' performance can be improved by ensuring appropriate recognition and reward for their efforts, and by improving communication, learning and work arrangements.

2.4 Organizational Leadership and Organizational Performance

Pirayeh et al. (2011) argues that a leader who wish to bring about organizational change in today's volatile business world, must practice the moral art of value-based leadership. The author adds that organizational success does not hinge on the various change strategies that are available. He suggests that programmes, and processes must be complied with for success to be achieved. Nonetheless, valued-based leaders may encounter different challenges, and practice different leadership style, but they all exhibit courage, integrity, authenticity, vision, and passion (Nanjundewaraswamy and Swamy,

2014; Neumam, 2007; Pirayeh et al., 2011). Such leaders lead by example, rather than by power; and they inspire trust, hope, and action, in their followers. Nanjundewaraswamy and Swamy (2014) opines that successful corporate leaders are dedicated to institutionalizing continuous change, renewal, innovation, and learning. Cole (2002) stresses that there is need to develop the idea of the environmental element and the power position of the leader in relation to organization culture and performance. Neumam (2007) in a study of the effectiveness of democratic, authoritarian and laissez-faire leadership styles observed that authoritarian leadership impaired initiative and bred hostility and aggressiveness while other styles were effective in creating better morale and attitudes among organizational employees. Moi et al. (2001) is of the opinion that by seeking to lead, one is helping the organization to remain competitive and grow, and this create opportunities for individuals to enrich their careers and personal lives. Mambula (2009) notes that leadership is one of the most important factors affecting organizational performance. He argues that for a manager, leadership means focusing on the activities through which the goals and objectives of the organization are accomplished. Whereas Duncan (2002) perceive leaders as a focus of group process, act of inducing compliance, the exercise of influence, a set of personality characteristics, the exercise of influence, an act of behaviour, a form of persuasion, an instrument of goal achievement, an effect of interaction, a differential role and initiation of structure. In the study of Cohen and Elmick (2002), the role of leadership is to obtain resources and deploy those resources to motivate staff members to perform. It is also a leader's role to ensure that the organization's performance results in accomplishments that serve public needs. In order to achieve this, managers of public organizations must engage in entrepreneurial risks taking. Duygulu and Ozeren (2009) defines leadership as the process wherein an individual member of a group or organization influences the interpretation of events, choice of objectives and strategies, the organization of work activities, the motivation of people to achieve the objectives, the maintenance of cooperative relationships, the development of skills and confidence by members, and the enlistment of support and cooperation from people outside the group or organization. Kreitner (2007) describes leadership as a process of inspiring, influencing, and guiding others to participate in common effort. In today's highly interconnected world, leadership extends beyond the office door or factory gate. To encourage such broad participation, leaders supplement any authority and power they possess with their personal attributes, imagination, and social skills. Dalton (2005) says a leader bear the responsibility of guiding a host of constituents toward the accomplishment of an overall goal, whether this will be leading employees toward greater productivity, guiding supplier toward a better understanding of ways to cooperate in order to better serve the firm's customers or helping investors appreciate the firm's strategy and how achievement of that strategy will result in enhanced shareholder value. Cole (2002) maintains that leadership is important at all levels within the company, from main board to the shop floor. Leadership is the moral and intellectual ability to visualize and work for what is best for the company and its employees. Mullins (2005) notes that leadership is related to motivation, interpersonal behaviour and the process of communication. Leadership is also important in attempting to reduce employee dissatisfaction. Good leadership involves the effective process of delegation and empowerment. Leadership must be operated under complex and uncertain circumstances. A leader under the right circumstances, can have a powerful impact on group performance.

Nanjundewaraswamy and Swamy (2014) observes that, leadership is important because top managers evaluate managers on their leadership potentials. Leadership is important because it contributes to organizational effectiveness. On the negative side there are many studies which show that lack of leadership leads to lower employee satisfaction, higher grievances, and low productivity.

2.5 Leadership Styles and Organizational Performance

Deal and Kennedy (2000) argues that the way leaders manage employees in an organization is known as leadership style. The researchers mentions further that there are four leadership styles found in situational leadership model; they are; high task low relationship, high task high relationship, high relationship low task and low relationship low task. Duygulu and Ozeren (2009) posit that several aspects of the work group affect the leadership process. Such as there are differences in abilities, skills, experiences, and cognitive style. In addition, some work groups are more experienced than the leader (Cole, 2002; Duncan, 2002; Duygulu and Ozeren, 2009). In the same view, groups differ in their attitudes toward leadership and the needs and motives of the individuals within the group. Additionally, groups differ in their expectations of the leader's personality, behaviour, and leadership style. Such expectations are based on experiences with past leaders. Duncan (2002) finds that leadership style that work for one person may not work for another person. Harari (2002) stresses that effective leadership is exercised across a full spectrum of responsibilities, and also over time. The author adds that across an entire organization, involving a wide variety of people engaged in a multitude of task, the leader must speak high performance and ensure the welfare of the group. Bello-Imam and Ojeifo (2007) reports that autocratic decision, consultative, joint decision and delegation are the four broad categories of leadership styles managers adopt in their relationship with employees. However, these broad categories of leadership orientation has traditionally been seen generally in empirical literature as yielding two broad bands of leadership, namely the task masters and the relationists. Jin (2010) opines that the task masters are leaders who are autocratic or directive-oriented with high concern for the job or production. While Sharma and Sharma (2010) argues that the relationists, on the other hand, apply a human face to leadership, they respect, regard, empower and support their workforce. Starling (2008) reports four basic leadership styles are developed by late William Reddin are; supporting or human relations style. The manager in this category has below average task orientation and above average relationship orientation. Coaching or participative style indicates managers have above average task orientation and above average relationship orientation. Delegating or laissez-fair manager has above task orientation and below average relationship orientation style. Hence, the manager has below average task orientation and below average relationship orientation. Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy (2014) are of the view that different leadership styles may affect organizational effectiveness or performance. Jin (2010) opines that transformational leadership integrates the elements of empathy, compassion, sensitivity, relationship building and innovation. Sharma and Sharma (2010) posits that transformational leaders help in the shaping and maintaining of desired organizational culture which may have a certain link to organizational effectiveness.

2.6 Organizational Culture and Organizational Performance

Deal and Kennedy (2000) defines organizational culture as the fabric of values, beliefs, assumptions, myths, norms, goals, and visions that are widely shared in the organization. Okibo and Shikanda (2016) opines that organizational culture forms an essential part of the functions of the organization. The authors adds that it is the moral fiber of the organization which describes and contains the organization's basic values. Alban-Metcalf (2016) believes that people feel intimidated about revealing their disability because of fears that they will be seen as less competent. Nonetheless, if people do not feel comfortable disclosing that they have disabilities, targets cannot be accurately monitored or reviewed. Hence, it is important that from the outset, the culture of the organization is one which demonstrates that people with disabilities are regarded as component and are genuinely valued in the workforce. Alnasser et al. (2016) opines that organizational culture has a strong relationship with organizational performance. Cole (2002) describes organizational culture as values, beliefs, behaviours, that differentiate one organization from the other. Pearse and Kanyanyale (2003) defines organizational culture as a set of expected behaviours that are generally supported within a particular group. Past researchers have reported a strong relationship between organizational culture and organizational performance (Fay and Dension, 2003; Pirayeh et al., 2011). According to Pearse and Kanyangale (2003), there is cultural difference between large and small organizations. Duncan (2002) finds that organizational culture can either be strong or weak. However, the author put forward that strong organizational culture can aid the organization in achieving high performance. The researcher further elucidates that artefacts, language, behaviour patterns, norms of behaviour, heroes, symbols and symbolic actions believes, values, attitudes, basic assumption and history are methods of learning organizational culture. Desson and Clouthier (2010) perceives that culture is a key factor not only in achieving organizational goals, but in attracting and keeping desirable employees, creating a positive public image, and building respectful relationships with stakeholders. Belias and Koustelios (2014) argues that culture is the sum of the beliefs that shape norms of behaviour and dictate the ways things get done in any organization. Alnasser et al. (2016) believes that the core of culture is formed by values and norms which are not visible but shared by people in the organization and this guides their behaviour in decision making. Ahmadi et al. (2012) concludes that organizational culture include beliefs, assumptions, values that members share, rule of conduct, leadership styles, administrative procedure, rituals and customs.

3.0 Methodology

Survey research method was used for the study, with questionnaire as an instrument for collecting the data. Newman (2007) opines that the survey research method is appropriate quantitative data collection because the questions are quicker and easier to answer by respondents, Yin (2012) adds that it is an appropriate method for research questions about selfreported beliefs or behaviour. Purposive sampling was adopted for this study. The sampled population consists of all staffs of Afrimedia totaling 40. All the respondents were administered with questionnaires which were completed and returned to the researcher. These include the Directors, Managers and the subordinate staff, with the help of two research assistants. In determining the sample size, the researcher chose to interview all staffs of the organization since the study is based on a single case study approach which involve emphasizing on one

particular organization with its constituent elements (Otokiti 2005; Meriam and Simpson, 1984; Yin, 2012). This study adopts both primary and secondary sources of data. The primary source of data used questionnaire while the secondary data used include textbooks, journals, previous research works, Internet and magazines. Creswell (2012) suggests that the selection of instrument for a research should consider such factors as the nature of the study. The questionnaire is divided into two sections, section A, comprises of general information, like age, gender, educational qualification and years of experience. While section B, comprises ten questions, which also include the research questions. All the questionnaires were completed and analyzed using simple percentage. The questionnaire form was defined as a collection of items to which a respondent is expected to react in writing (Yin, 2009; Creswell, 2007). Being the main instrument used for data collection, the questionnaire comprised well-designed questions administered to the target population of 40 participants who are employees and management staffs of the organization. The choice of this instrument enabled us to obtain well stipulated information from the respondents whom we considered could give valid or more accurate answers. This approach was used because it helps the researchers understand the management and leadership styles adopted in the case study organization. The purposive or judgmental sampling technique was used for this research which is a technique whereby the researcher uses his/her judgment in selecting the subjects from the population for study based on some identified parameters (Yin, 2009; Ajagbe et al., 2015).

3.1 Research Objectives

- a) Find out what leadership considers as organizational culture.
- b) Whether leadership and organizational culture impact on performance.
- c) To find out what leadership style exist in the company.
- d) Find out ways members access organizational culture.

3.2 Research Questions

- a) What do leadership considers as organizational culture?
- b) How does leadership and organizational culture impact on performance?
- c) What type of leadership style exist in the company?
- d) What ways do members access organizational culture?

4.0 Data Analysis

Table1: Leadership Consideration of Organizational Culture

Variables	Responses	Percentage of Responses
Integrity, security, high ethical standard	5	12.50
Security, routine process, moral ethical standard, integrity, continuous learning	23	57.50

High ethical standard, Routine process, continuous learning	10	25.00
Routine process, high moral standard	2	5.00
Total	40	100.00

Majority 23(57.50%) of the respondents said security, routine process, moral ethical standard, integrity and continuous learning are considered by leaders as organizational culture in the company. While 10(25.00%) of the respondents said high ethical standard, routine process and continuous learning are considered by leaders as organizational culture. Another 5(12.50%) of the respondents said integrity, security and high ethical standard are considered by leaders as organizational culture. Minority 2(5.00%) of the respondents said routine process, and high moral standard are considered as organizational culture.

Figure 2: Impact of Leadership and Organizational Culture on Performance

Majority 21(52.50%) of the respondents said leadership and organizational culture impact on performance through, rewards and promotions to encourage competitive behaviour, culture that is receptive to change and good working relations among directors and managers, and between managers and subordinate staff. Another 11(27.50%) of the respondents said leadership and organizational culture impact on performance through, good working relations among different sections, clear organizational objectives and culture of commitment. 4(10.00%) of the respondents said leadership and organizational culture impact on performance through organizational culture that is receptive to change, good working relations with other staff and the use of rewards and sanctions. Another

4(10.00%) of the respondents said leadership and organizational culture impact on performance through good leadership, management skills and clear organizational objectives.

Figure 3: RQ 3: Leadership Style in Practice

Majority 20(50.00%) of the respondents said the leadership style in practice in the company is transformational. While 14(35.00%) of the respondents said leadership style in practice in the company are transformational and transactional leadership styles. Minority 6(15.00%) of the respondents said leadership style in practice in the company is transactional leadership style.

Figure 4: RQ 4: Assessment of Organizational Culture by Members

Majority 18(45.00%) of the respondents said ways members access organizational culture in the company are language, behaviour pattern, history, symbols, symbolic actions, believe, attitude and

values. Another 9(22.50%) of the respondents said ways members access organizational culture in the company are, leaders playing role model, through learning and communication of leader's belief. Minority 3(7.50%) of the respondents said ways members access organizational culture in the company are through imposition of culture, appointment and keeping employees who think like their leaders.

5.0 Findings and Discussions

The result of this study shows that security, routine process, moral ethical standard, integrity and continuous learning are considered by leaders as organizational culture. The study also finds that the variables considered to constitute what organizational culture is in a particular advertising agency may not necessarily be the same in other advertising agencies. Nonetheless, organizational culture varies from organizations to organizations. This study further reveals that majority of the respondents reported that organizational leadership and organizational culture impact on organizational performance through, rewards and promotions. This is aimed at encouraging competitive behavior, culture that is receptive to change and good working relations among directors and managers. Hence, these findings are consistent with that of Madu (2010), Yukl (2008), Mambulla (2009), Chandle and Black (2007) and Alnasseri et al. (2016) who finds in their study that organizational leadership and organizational culture impact on organizational performance. On top of this, organizational leadership styles in practice in the advertising agency was found to be transformational in nature, as also reported by Sharma and Sharma (2010) and Jin (2010), that transformational style has empathy, compassion, sensitivity, relationship building and innovation which help to shape and maintain organizational culture resulting in organizational performance. The outcome of this study also reveals that the ways members access organizational culture are language, behaviour pattern, history, symbols, symbolic actions, believe, attitude and values. This agrees with Biliias and Koustelios (2014) who finds that the following are approach of learning organizational culture; these include, artefacts, language, behaviour patterns, norms of behaviour, heroes, symbols and symbolic actions, believes, values, attitudes, basic assumption and history.

6.0 Conclusion

Leadership and organizational culture are both intertwined and interwoven and therefore cannot be separated. An organization is said to be strong or weak depending on whether it has strong or weak culture. Leaders or founders are the originators of organizational culture. Hence, all organizations no matter how big or small have one form of culture or the other. Organizational culture therefore determines the performance of any organization. From the findings, this study concludes that organizational leadership and organizational culture are important in the overall performance of any organization. Organizational culture is linked to organizational performance, on top of this, security, routine process, moral and high ethical standard, integrity and continuous learning are considered as organizational culture in an advertising agency. The purpose of introducing organizational culture by organizational leadership is to achieve organizational goals. Therefore, organizational leadership and organizational culture can only impact on organizational performance when employees see leadership put in place reward and promotion, encourage healthy competitive behaviour, culture that is receptive to change, good working relationship between the leadership and the subordinates. The style adopted by the leadership of an organization determines whether or not the organization is able to attain their

objectives. Transformational leaders are said to be change agents and charismatic in nature. Organizations that are successful are those organizations that give employees access to organizational culture through language, behaviour pattern, history, symbols, symbolic actions, believe, attitudes and values. The limitation of this study is that a single case study approach was used to gather data for this study. Findings from this study may not necessarily be generalized but could be an addition to the body of existing literature. Future authors are advised to adopt a wide array of sample population in order to improve on the generalizability of findings.

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